

Polystyrene based shape memory nanocomposites

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SUMMARY

Shape memory nanocomposites were fabricated using cross-link polystyrene as a matrix and different nano-fillers (including alumina, silica and clay) were used as the enhancing agencies. Their thermo-mechanical properties and shape memory effect (SME) were characterized using micro-indentation, tensile tests and differential scanning calorimetry. Experimental results clearly revealed the reinforcement effect from the nanofillers, good thermal properties and SME.

Keywords: Shape memory, nanocomposites, polystyrene, mechanical properties

1. Introduction

Shape memory polymer (SMP) can recover its original shape from large deformation and extended period of cold hibernation, as triggered by external stimulations such as heat [1], electric field [2], magnetic field [3], and light [4]. The basic shape memory mechanism is based on a reversible energy conversion in polymer chain movement. For thermal actuation mechanism, the transition temperature is related to the melting temperature or glass transition temperature of polymers [5]. SMP offers a much higher degree of deformation and a wider scope of varying mechanical properties compared to shape memory alloys or ceramics, in addition to their inherent advantages of being cheap and biocompatibility, light weight, and easy processability [6]. However, the mechanical strength of the soft SMP materials limits their applications. One way to improve it is to introduce different nanofillers into the polymer matrix to reinforce the material [7,8], i.e. so-called nanocomposite SMP. In the nanocomposites, the dispersed particles of smaller than 100 nm in at least one dimension can effectively enhance the matrix. There are different fabrication process to synthesize the nanocomposites such as in-situ polymerization, sol-gel process, etc, which have recently attracted great attentions in the field of organic-inorganic nanocomposites.

Polystyrene (PS) has been widely used as hard segments in copolymer for nanocomposite design and applications, because of its low cost comparing to the other tough polymers such as PMMA, polyurethane, or polycarbonate, etc. Some studies have

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been carried out on the shape memory property of polystyrene based SMPs [9,10], etc, but there are few reports on the PS based nanocomposite design and fabrication. This paper presents a systematic study on the processing and characterization of the cross linking PS based shape memory nanocomposites with different nano-fillers.

2. Experimental

Styrene based prepolymer and benzyl peroxide (BPO) based curing agents were obtained from CRG Company, USA. The nano-fillers include nano attapulgite clay [11], nano SiO₂ and nano Al₂O₃ powders. All fillers were kept in oven at 120°C for 24 hours to remove the moisture. They were mixed with prepolymer for 15min, followed by ultrasonic treatment for 30 min. The mixture was kept stirring for 15min after adding curing agent, then ultrasonically agitated for 15 min. Samples were prepared by casting the mixture into PTFE moulds and baked at 75°C for 36 hours.

Micro-hardness (Vickers) testing was performed on samples with an average hardness reading calculated from at least five indentation tests. The indentation load was fixed at 245mN with the indentation time 20s. DSC analysis was performed using a Thermal Advantage DSC 2010 at a heating rate of 10°C/min under a constant nitrogen flow. Tensile tests were carried out using an Instron Universal Testing Instrument (Type 5567) at a constant tensile speed of 5mm/min at room temperature (20°C). Thermo-mechanical cycle tests were performed to investigate the shape memory effect of the SMP and nanocomposites. Fig. 1 (a) and (b) shows the schematic drawings of the thermo-mechanical cycle. The specimen was loaded to a strain (ϵ_m) at a constant crosshead speed of 5 mm/min at a temperature T_{high} (stage 1). Then, it was cooled to the temperature T_{low} while holding the same strain ϵ_m (stage 2). After 5 min at the temperature T_{low} , the load on the specimen was released (stage 3), and the unloaded specimen was heated from T_{low} to T_{high} in 5 min (stage 4). One thermo-mechanical cycle consisted of four stages and then the test was repeated to 4 cycles. The basic conditions and definitions in cycle test were as follows: $\epsilon_m=100\%$; $T_{high}=60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{low}=20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, ϵ_e =Strain after unloading, ϵ_p = Permanent strain.

Fig. 1. Schematic drawings of cyclic tensile testing: (a) 2-D and (b) 3-D, There are four steps in each cycle: (1) stretching to ϵ_m at T_{high} ; (2) cooling to T_{low} while ϵ_m is kept constant; (3) keeping shape at T_{low} ; (4) keeping shape in T_{low} , heating up to T_{high} ; then start of the second cycle.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Optimization of the curing process

The fabrication process investigation was focused on the curing stage, during which the cross link network was formed. Baking time was considered as a major factor in cross linking kinetics. As shown in Fig. 2, the hardness increases significantly at the initial stage because the cross link rate increases with baking time. The hardness becomes stable after the baking time was prolonged to 36hrs. From the DSC results shown in Fig. 2(b), the polymer transition temperature (T_{trans}) increases from 45.8 °C to 60.4 °C as the baking time was increased to 72hrs. The T_{trans} increases as a symbol of growing of the cross link rate. The hardness results and thermal study showed that the cross link rate was improved by prolonging the cross link time. The optimized curing time for this study was selected as 36 hours.

Fig.2 Effects of the curing time on Pure PS (a) Vicker's hardness; (b) DSC traces

3.2 Mechanical Properties of the nanocomposite

Fig. 3(a) shows the Vicker's hardness results of all three kinds of nanocomposites as a function of nano particles content. Significant increase of hardness was observed with the addition of the nano particles. For example, with 4wt % content of the treated clay powder, the microhardness reaches a maximum value of about 75MPa, which is nearly 400% improvement compared to that of the pure PS. The Al_2O_3 nano particles show similar hardness reinforcement with the treated clay, and the SiO_2 nanoparticles performed the weakest enhancement: the hardness only doubled when the SiO_2 content reached 4 wt%. Composites with 1% nano-fillers were selected to do the tensile test with the purpose to compare their stress-strain relation at room temperature (20°C). The typical strain-stress curves (Fig. 3(b)) clearly reveal the stress-strain relationship for the samples with the same filler content. From the maximum stress and breaking strain results shown in Fig. 3(c), the SiO_2/PS composites obtain nearly 16% increasing in peak stress, and the Al_2O_3/PS composites present a better enhancement as the maximum stress nearly doubled. The clay nanocomposites have a maximum stress which is 120% more than that of pure PS, and have a breaking strain about 75% of that for the pure PS sample. The Young's Modulus results (shown in Fig. 3(d)) from the tensile test exhibited that the clay/PS composites had the best enhancement, nearly 300% of the pure PS.

The percolating structure of the fillers can result in dramatic increases in the reinforcement efficiency. With adding a critical volume fraction of rods (such as nano-clay), the nanorods stretch and perturb the domains of the matrix, and the polymer blend confines nanorods, generate elongated domains that are reinforced by these fillers [12]. The superior enhancement of nano filler with plates and rods structures compared with sphere nano-particles have been predicted and proved in homopolymer system, because the stress concentration was reduced and transferred by the high aspect ratio and specific particle geometry [13]. In this study, the remarkable improvement of mechanical properties with 1% clay compared with other sphere fillers can be explained by this reason. Fig. 4 shows that the tensile stress increases significantly with clay content up to 1 %, then decreases with further addition of nano-clay. Fig. 4(c) shows that Young's modulus increases significantly with addition of nano-clay. For example, with 1% clay addition, the modulus is almost 3 times higher than that of pure PS. The similar enhancement was reported in ref. [11]. The decrease in enhancement after adding more than 1% clay could be attributed to poor organic-inorganic interface as reported in Ref. [14,16]. The inefficient mixing causes agglomeration of nanoparticle rather than dispersing homogeneously in matrix.

Fig.3. Mechanical properties comparison for samples: (a). Vicker's hardness results with 25g load and 20s load time; (b). tensile results at room temperature; (c). fracture strain and max stress from tensile tests; (d) the Young's modulus from tensile tests

Fig.4. Tensile results for clay/PS nano composites: (a). stress-strain curve; (b). fracture strain and max stress analysis; (c). Young's modulus as a function of clay percentage

3.3 Thermal properties of the nanocomposites

DSC tests are summarized in Fig. 5. With the addition of the nano particles from 1% to 3%, the transition temperatures decrease slightly, less than 3°C. The clay/PS composites show the smallest decrease in the reduction of temperature among the three types of nanocomposites as presented in Fig. 5(b). From both Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it can be concluded that the treated clay presents the best performance on enhancement and preventing the reduction of T_{trans} than the others. As reported, homogenous dispersing of nano particles in matrix is difficult to achieve if without additional treatment on the fillers [15,16], therefore, aggregation of nano-fillers in the nanocomposites will cause some negative effects such as decrease in the transition temperature. Liu [17] revealed that transition temperature of cross link polymer depended on the crosslink rate. In this study, incorporating of nano particles could cause a reduction of cross linking point by preventing formation of the cross link bond, which directly results in a decline in cross link rate.

Fig.5. Thermal property investigation on T_{tran} for all samples : (a).Silica/PS; (b).Clay/PS; (c). Al_2O_3 /PS; (d). evolution of T_{tran} with content of nano-fillers

3.4 Thermo-mechanical cycle property

When the external stress is applied to a SMP, soft/flexible segment will be preferentially extended in the stress direction relative to the hard/fixed segment. The shape memory properties are normally evaluated in terms of percentage in shape recovery and shape fixity [18,19]. As shown in Fig. 6, stress–strain curves for thermo-mechanical cyclic tensile test with a fixed strain can clearly show the shape recovery behavior. The results indicate that, at a high temperature of 60 $^{\circ}C$, the maximum stress of pure PS (1.45 MPa) is about 50% of that in room temperature as shown in Fig. 4(b). The similar behaviors are also observed in the nanocomposites. Shape memory macromolecules system turns elastic when temperature reaches above the transition temperature as the molecule chain become flexible from “freezing”, this results in the reduction in the maximum stress. The maximum stress of 1% clay/PS nanocomposites was the highest among all the samples, showing a good enhancement even at the temperature above T_{trans} . When the cyclic tensile stretch proceeds, the residual strain ϵ_p increases. Several reasons may lead

to this, for example, the random breaking of covalent cross-link bond, the energy storing by the fillers [20], the blocking effect by incorporating nano-fillers [12], etc.

Fig.6. Thermal mechanical cyclic testing results: (a). pure PS; (b). 0.5% Clay/PS composites; (c). 1% Clay/PS composites; (d). 2% Clay/PS composites

The shape memory effect was evaluated using strain recovery ratio at cycle number N as defined by Eq. (1) [15]. The strain recovery ratio considering the residual strain per each cycle was used [15]:

$$R_r(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_u(N) - \varepsilon_p(N)}{\varepsilon_u(N) - \varepsilon_p(N-1)} \quad (1)$$

where $R_r(N)$ is the strain recovery ratio in the cycle number N , $\varepsilon_u(N)$ is the unloading strain at T_{low} in the cycle number N , $\varepsilon_p(N)$ and $\varepsilon_p(N-1)$ are residual strain in the cycle number N and $N-1$. Figure 7 presents recovery rates with the numbers of cyclic tests. It has been found that the recovery rates of all samples are above 85%. However, the recovery rate of 2% clay composites decreased nearly 15% compared with the pure PS, as the consequence of non-uniform fillers dispersing in polymer, and the random destruction in covalent cross-link bond. A good retention of recovery rate also was

discovered, which indicates that they remain stable strain recovery ability after several cyclic tests.

Fig.7. Recovery rate versus cyclic numbers of samples

3.5 Shape memory recovery

Film samples with a thickness of 0.6 mm and width of 10 mm was rolled after heating to 90°C, and kept the shape during cooling to room temperature (20°C). The shape recovery test was carried out in hot water with 60°C. The pure PS sample (see Fig. 8) exhibited a prompt response in hot water, recovering its original shape within 20s. The nanocomposites (see Fig.9) with 1 % clay show faster recovery than that of the pure PS, recovering within 12s. The reason could be explained from that the T_{trans} decreases with adding of clay.

Fig.8. The recovery procedure of SMPs film in hot water of 60°C

A micro-gripper based on pure PS was manufactured through laser cutting as shown in Fig. 10. The shape recovery of the gripper at a temperature of 80°C was demonstrated. The maximum recovery displacement can be as large as 2mm. A five penny coin was

used as a comparison of the dimension. This SMP microgripper can be used for the potential biomedical or microassembly application.

Fig.9 The recovery procedure of 1% treated clay/PS composites in hot water at 60°C

Fig.10 Shape recovery of micro-gripper based on pure PS

4. Conclusion

The PS based shape memory nanocomposites were studied in this paper. Nano particles brought an effective enhancement to the SMP matrix, and the treated clay achieved the best results in the improvement in strength. The DSC results showed a slight decrease in T_{trans} with addition of nanoparticles for all the composites samples. The nanoclay presents superior properties on the enhancement and preventing the reduction of T_{trans}

than the others. Thermal cyclic testing indicates that the recovery rates of all samples are above 85%, and good strain recovery ability was demonstrated.

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